

Containing complexity: Networks of expertise and the emergence of genetic epidemiology, 1900–1990

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In the years since the Human Genome Project's completion, it has become increasingly uncontroversial to describe the project as having inflated expectations. With genetic knowledge neither as comprehensible nor as utilisable as the genomic decade suggested, making sense of the human genome is now a computational endeavour reliant on bioinformatics (Salter and Salter 2017) and, increasingly, machine learning (Nicholls et al 2020). These techniques are hoped to unlock genomic variation and make real headway in complex causality, and have spurred new forecasting that by 2030, “the biological function(s) of every human gene will be known” and “the clinical relevance of all encountered genomic variants will be readily predictable” (Green et al 2020: 690).

Figure 1. Citation network of literature relevant to the development of genetic epidemiology, showing only 13 largest clusters ($n=7,309$; $m=17,064$). Nodes positioned via ForceAtlas2. Node size proportional to indegree. Node colour depicts cluster membership of the 13 largest clusters.

This paper takes the contemporary problem of complexity in human genomic research backwards in time, by examining how earlier encounters with complex causality were contained within a particular subfield: genetic epidemiology. Genetic epidemiology is both a fairly young and a fairly unknown subfield in human genetics research, with a single flagship journal, *Genetic Epidemiology*, launched in 1984. However, some of the most influential publications in 20th and 21st century genetics are intimately connected with genetic epidemiology and its genesis, including the proposal for genome-wide association studies (Risch and Merikangas 1996) that ushered in the ongoing era of large-scale, population-based genomic analyses. In this analysis, we seek to uncover the unseen influence of genetic epidemiology by tracing how the subfield

developed over the course of the 20th century. More particularly, we suggest that subspecialties within the emergent discipline helped to “contain” problems involving complex causality in distinct networks of expertise, resulting in a weakly-connected interdisciplinary network that would later be threatened by replication crises during the initial years of the Human Genome Project (Risch 1990; Arribas-Ayllon et al 2010). However, we also suggest that stronger connections between statisticians and biometricians within this network helped support both the constitution of genetic epidemiology as a distinct subfield and the later translation of statistical genetic techniques into population-level analyses, as with the development of genome-wide association studies.

Using bibliometric and citation network analysis (Leng and Leng 2021), we recreate a publication history of genetic epidemiology, from the early 20th century up to the beginning of the replication crisis in the 1990s. Citation network analysis refers to the application of graph theory and network science to bibliographic data. Citation networks consist of nodes that represent individual papers, with directed edges between nodes representing citations from a citing to a cited paper. Such networks allow for the analysis and visualisation of the structure of the scientific literature into specific topics, fields, and disciplines. This structure is self-organising; papers on the same or similar topics cluster together into densely interacting literatures due to the tendency of authors to cite other papers directly relevant to their own (Price, 1965). To understand how a literature clusters into distinct topics of areas, modularity maximisation (Newman & Girvan, 2004) via the Leiden Algorithm is a common and well validated approach (Klavans & Boyack 2017; Traag et al., 2019). By these methods, citation networks have been used to produce ‘maps’ of literatures in a number of different areas. Recent examples include sustainability sciences (Kajikawa et al. 2014), oxytocin research (Leng & Leng, 2021; Leng et al. 2022), as well as emerging topics in energy storage (Mejia & Kajikawa, 2020) and immunology (Fujii et al. 2022). Beyond its use in literature discovery and survey, it is used to test for citation bias and error propagation in evidence-bases informing the evaluation of specific hypotheses (Greenberg, 2009; Leng 2018).

Our citation network consists of 10,412 articles (nodes) and 23,514 citations (edges), drawn from two searches of Web of Science indexing. The first search consisted of 97 terms and targeted epidemiological journals, returning a total of 2,889 documents. The second search consisted of 107 terms (including many shared) and targeted genetics journals, returning a total of 3,227 documents. From this total literature of 5,860 documents, we retrieved all associated metadata from Web of Science in March 2024, and restructured these data in the R statistical environment into: 1) a ‘Node-attribute list’ that contains (i) a unique ID for each unique reference string; (ii) WoS unique identifier number; (iii) DOI (if available); (iv) name of all authors; (v) title of paper; (vi) journal of publication; (vii) year of publication; (viii) total number of citations recorded by WoS; and (ix) total number of references recorded by WoS and 2) an ‘Edge-list’ built from the bibliographies of retrieved papers that contains two columns – Source and Target. Source contains the unique ID of the citing paper, while Target contains the unique ID of the cited paper.

In addition to our retrieved dataset of 5,860 nodes, we also include non-retrieved papers by constructing nodes from unique reference strings detected in the bibliographies of the retrieved papers. This expands our dataset to 92,327 nodes (5,860 retrieved and 86,467 unretrieved) connected by 140,947 citation links. We then refine this set first by restricting the network to the largest connected component of 88,454 nodes (~95.8% of set) and 137,678 edges (~97.7%), discarding 3,873 papers that neither cite nor are cited directly by the other retrieved papers in the largest interconnected component, and nor share common references to non-retrieved documents. We further refined the network to include only documents published before 1990, resulting in a dataset of 13,559 documents and 23,597 citation links. Again, we restrict to the largest main component formed, excluding unconnected documents from this structure – the network has 10,412 nodes and 23,514 edges, of which 2,280 are retrieved documents.

We clustered the network via modularity maximisation with the Leiden algorithm, resulting in 41 clusters at $Q=0.786$. For now, we focus on the 13 largest in terms of number of retrieved papers (see attached Figure 1) and categorize them by topic (see attached Table 1), which we discerned by reading a sample of the literature in each. For our preliminary analysis, we examine citation trends within the overall network relative to specific time intervals, exploring how papers accumulate citations over time and which clusters within the network are receiving most citations at given time periods. We calculate citation metrics using both cumulative counts and period-specific counts to understand citation trends per paper, using five-year time intervals: 1918-1930 (combined due to small number of total citations during this period), 1931-35; 1936-

1940; 1941-1945; 1946-1950; 1951-55; 1956-1960; 1961-1965; 1966-1970; 1971-1975; 1976-1980; 1981-85; 1986-1990.

Focusing on period-specific counts, we track several trends in citations that correspond to the emergent network of genetic epidemiology. Although prior to 1960 most papers in the dataset had very few, if any, citations, in the period 1965-1970 work in statistical genetics began to receive more attention, with the top-cited paper for this period, “Sequential tests for the detection of linkage” (Morton, N.E., *American Journal of Human Genetics* 1955), growing from 3 cumulative citations in the preceding period (1960-1965) to 14. More generally, of the 30 most-cited papers within this period, 13 fell within three clusters strongly associated with statistical genetic techniques (Cluster 0 and Cluster 4) and population-level analysis of genetic conditions (Cluster 8), and 7 within two clusters associated with genetic studies of chronic and complex diseases (Cluster 2 and Cluster 3). This trend continues in the next time period, 1971-1975, with 19 of the top-cited papers falling within Clusters 0, 4, and 8, and the top-cited paper for the period, “The inheritance to liability of certain diseases” (Falconer, D.S., *Annals of Human Genetics* 1965) showing a growth in cumulative citations from 7 in the period 1965-1970 to 18 in 1971-1975.

Our ongoing analysis continues this time period assessment through to 1990, and will involve more in-depth review of highly-cited literature and of the limitations of citation analysis. We plan to refine our network further by revising our search terms to include several terms missed in the initial searches, to capture the largest possible universe of relevant literature. Finally, we intend to examine how the largest interconnected component of the network changes over time, to assess how new developments in statistical genetic methods are referenced by empirical analyses in other disciplines.

Cluster	Total count	Retrieved count	Topic
1	981	219	Genetic linkage mapping
0	1040	204	Estimation of genetic and nongenetic factors in quantitative trait variation
2	902	177	Genetic aspects of various psychiatric disorders
4	546	153	Genetic linkage analysis
3	574	126	Genetic approaches to diabetes mellitus
8	417	120	Incidence and associations of suspected inherited or genetic disorders, particularly congenital
9	388	113	Polymorphism discoveries, largely in blood factors
5	509	109	Experimental genetics of quantitative traits (non-human)
6	486	96	Genetic aspects of cancer (particularly breast, colon and melanoma)
11	346	96	Experimental genetics of susceptibility and resistance to infectious disease (non-human)
10	377	88	Genetic linkage analysis and biostatistics (nonhuman)
14	286	80	Molecular genetics and molecular genetic linkage
7	457	76	“Formal” genetic epidemiology

Table 1. 13 Largest clusters based on retrieved count, with topic categories.

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